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PРАВНА ЗАШТИТА ДЕТЕТА НАКОН ПРЕСТАКА ЗАЈЕДНИЦЕ ЖИВОТА РОДИТЕЛЈА

Cilj rada jeste da se kroz teorijsku, normativnu i empirijsku analizu sagleda položaj deteta nakon prestanka zajednice života roditelja, sa akcentom na njegovo pravo da održava lične odnose sa roditeljem s kojim ne živi, kao i sa bliskim srođnicima (baba, deka, tetka, ujak, stric). Pitanje kontakta deteta sa roditeljem koji ne vrši roditeljsko pravo predstavlja jedan od najsloženijih aspekata porodičnopravnih odnosa, jer se u praksi često sukobljavaju interesi roditelja, emocionalne potrebe deteta i ograničenja institucionalnih mehanizama zaštite. Autorka polazi od teze da je zaštita prava deteta na kontakt neodvojiva od šireg pojma pravne zaštite deteta kao najosetljivijeg subjekta u društvu. Dete, kao nosilac posebnih prava i potreba, ne može samo da štiti svoje interese, pa država ima pozitivnu obavezu da obezbedi njihovo poštovanje, kako kroz zakonodavni okvir, tako i kroz efikasnu sudsku i institucionalnu praksu. Istraživanje ukazuje da je ovo pravo često ugroženo u situacijama razvoda braka, prestanka vanbračne zajednice, roditeljskih konflikata i pojava roditeljskog otuđenja. U takvim okolnostima, neophodna je aktivna intervencija države, organa starateljstva i pravosudnih institucija radi očuvanja kontinuiteta detetovih emocionalnih i socijalnih veza.

Ključne reči: prava deteta, pravna zaštita deteta, najbolji interes deteta, porodično pravo, roditeljsko pravo, kontakt deteta sa roditeljem, kontakt deteta sa srođnicima.

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LEGAL PROTECTION OF THE CHILD AFTER THE TERMINATION OF THE PARENTAL COMMUNITY OF LIFE

The aim of the paper is to examine, through theoretical, normative and empirical analysis, the position of the child after the termination of the parental community of life, with specific reference to the children's right to maintain personal relations with the parent who does not live with the minor as well as with close relatives (grandparents, aunts, uncles). The issue of contact between a child and a parent who does not exercise parental rights is one of the most complex aspects of family law relations because the parents' interests, the emotional needs of the child, and the limitations of institutional protection mechanisms often conflict in practice. The author starts from the thesis that the protection of the child's right to contact is inseparable from the broader concept of legal protection of the child as the most sensitive subject in society. As a bearer of special rights and needs, the child cannot protect his/her own interests alone. Thus, the state has a positive obligation to ensure the observance of children's rights and interests, both through the legislative framework and through effective judicial and institutional practice. The conducted research indicates that this right is often threatened in situations of divorce, termination of cohabitation, parental conflicts and the occurrence of parental alienation. In such circumstances, active intervention by the state, guardianship authorities and judicial institutions is necessary to preserve the continuity of the child's emotional and social ties.

Keywords: rights of the child, children's legal protection, best interests of the child, family law, parental rights, child's contact with non-resident parent and relatives.